

LET THE FLOWER KNOW THE COLOR OF MY TONGUE; LET THE PEOPLE KNOW WHO I AM...

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Abstract. *The given article explores the mastery of Omon Matjon in creating literary images, with particular emphasis on his interpretation of the images of the nation's revered sons. The poet's lyrical works are subjected to analysis. It is highlighted that in his literary creations, the poet turns to legends and myths in order to reveal more deeply his inner turmoil, ideas, dreams, and aspirations. Special attention is paid to the fact that through the portrayal of historically real figures such as Pahlavon Mahmud, Beruni, and Najmiddin Kubro, the works address universal human issues.*

Keywords: *historical character, image, theme, idea, artistic depiction, historical truth, appearance, impression.*

Introduction

There are mountains in Khorezm indeed, there are!

The mountains of Khorezm,

so as not to block the oasis from the morning sun,

live in human form!

Khwarizmi,

Beruni,

Shaykh Najmiddin Kubro,

Zamakhshari,

Pahlavon Mahmud,

Ogahiy,

Hojikhon,

Komiljon...

Indeed, Khorezm is a land of great people-of unique talents, individuals whose intellect and wisdom have made a worthy contribution to world civilization, people with ocean-like hearts and faith as firm as mountains. Omon Matjon himself was one of these proud mountains of Khorezm. If the value of a mountain is measured by the richness of the minerals hidden in its depths, then the value of a poet is measured by the pearls and gems flowing from his pen. If we compare Omon Matjon's creative work to a mountain, it stands out for the vast scale of the immense spiritual treasure contained within it. This mountain holds many undiscovered secrets. Throughout his long creative journey, Omon Matjon accumulated a rich treasury, refined it, and sought to pass it on to future generations in its pure form. He took from the people and returned it to the people. As a generous son of Khorezm, he created images of many ancestors who devoted their lives to the homeland and made worthy contributions to its development.

In his lyrical poems, the Khorezm dialect reveals itself in a variety of expressive colors. He used the dialect skillfully; however, this did not occur at the expense of violating the norms of the literary language. Instead, dialectal features were employed to reveal the inner emotional world of his characters. This is one manifestation of the poet's mastery in creating artistic images. Definitely, Omon Matjon is a poet who does not shy away from speaking the truth. He elevated realism to a high level in poetry and deeply felt the pain of the people. His collections such as The

Caravan Bell (1973), The Sun Clock (1974), The Burning Tree (1976), The Wounded Lightning (1977), I Love You (1981), Trees and Herbs (1984), Only One Apple Between Us (1990), Man's Shadow Fell on the Sun (1991), The Path of Birds (1993), The Light of Faith (1994), Ardakhiva (2000), Pilgrimages of Khoja Ahror (2002), and others; as well as the poetry book The Cry of the Sacred Bird (40 legends, 1979) and the poetic novella Times That Speak (1986), embody folk sensibilities, philosophical reflections, and the subtle nuances of the human soul.

In the works of a poet, the themes of humanity, homeland, love, life, and truth occupy a special place. In particular, the concept of truth is the central point of Omon Matjon's life philosophy. He approaches this theme not only intellectually, but also spiritually, morally, and socially. He deeply feels that it is not easy to openly express the suffering of the people. He shares in the hardships and sorrows that his nation endured in the past century, standing with the people in their trials. He does not remain a silent spectator in the face of injustice and oppression. It is known to everyone that fire consumes everything. To make a fire blaze, one must keep adding fuel continuously. Similarly, the poet casts his poems into the fire like fuel; the verses, already glowing red from the heat of his heart, catch fire quickly and intensify the blaze. The fire gains strength. After all, if this fire could put an end to all injustice... let the poems burn and vanish. What matters is that the fire, in its own voice, conveys the poet's heartfelt emotions in vivid, multicolored tones.

Now I will not write it on paper,
I will write it on the blazing fire.
The multicolored slogans of the flames, the tones of the fire
Will express the burning in my heart!

In the poet's work, truth is often placed in stark contrast to falsehood, deceit, and hypocrisy. Omon Matjon criticizes the insincerity and duplicity present in the social environment of his time. In his view, a society that has lost truth also loses its human face. The creator entrusts his ideas to his characters, who carry them forward in the narrative. His heroes are historically great figures. He offers fresh interpretations of historically real personalities such as Pahlavon Mahmud, al-Biruni, Najmiddin Kubro, Alisher Navoi, Mashrab, and Shukur Burxon. He strives to reveal aspects of these figures that are little known to us. In creating his characters, Omon Matjon effectively employs artistic psychology. By "artistic psychology," we mean the revelation of a character's inner world, the psychological foundation of their actions and speech, and a set of techniques and tools that serve this purpose. In contemporary literature, the thoughts of a character are often conveyed through "internal monologue," a method widely used to depict the inner life of a person.

Omon Matjon is a poet who is innately devoted to the people. He always sees himself together with his people and loves his nation more than his own life. When he gives form to each image he creates, he обязательно endows it with a share of love for the people. As we know, Pahlavon Mahmud is remembered not only as a great wrestler, but also as a keen philosopher, a skillful poet, and a noble human being. His poems, philosophy, the philosophy of chivalry, and his moral legacy continue to serve as a source of inspiration for today's generation. The rubaiyat of Pahlavon Mahmud are rich in content, powerful in style, and marked by deep philosophical insight. Their spirit is close to the poetry of Khayyam, since Pahlavon Mahmud reflects in his verses on worldly philosophy, human life, and spiritual values:

*The world is like a golden jug,
At times its water is sweet,
At times bitter...*

Such lines reveal his profound philosophical outlook on life, humanity, and time.

In the dramatic epic “Pahlavon Mahmud,” Omon Matjon portrays Pahlavon Mahmud not only as a hero, poet, and craftsman, but also as a person who places his homeland and his people above worldly wealth. This aspect of his character is depicted in vivid colors. It is known that after winning wrestling contests in India and once rescuing Indian envoys who had gone to Khivak (Khiva), Pahlavon Mahmud earns the favor of the Indian king. The king presents him with a chest of precious stones. Pahlavon Mahmud refuses this gift and instead asks for as many Khivan captives as could fit within the area of a single horse’s hide. The Indian king immediately agrees to this condition and has the horse’s hide brought. However, Pahlavon Mahmud proves to be far cleverer than expected. He cuts the hide into thin strips, ties them together to make a long rope, and then encircles all those gathered to leave. Amazed by his heroism, the Indian king is now struck by his wisdom and virtue as well. He considers it dishonorable to go back on his word.

“I admire you! May your path be clear! A deal is a deal!”

“Go safely and return to your homeland,
O brave man!” the Indian king proclaims.

Those freed from captivity honor him, calling him “Our Deliverer.”

In truth, Pahlavon Mahmud is a proud, mountain-like son of Khorezm. For him, the freedom of his people is a value as lofty as honor and dignity. We can observe the creative intention of Omon Matjon, imbued with such people-centered and patriotic motifs, in his other works as well. In the poem by Omon Matjon “The Monologue of Shaykh Najmiddin Kubro,” Shaykh Najmiddin Kubro is depicted not only as a sharp-witted poet and religious leader, but also as a truth-seeking human being.

The pillars of the state grow strong for their own gain,
Plundering the poor, showing care only to the rich,
There is no justice among the people; outsiders are despised,
And if a mouth dares to speak, an iron net falls upon it—
Let them tear my heart to pieces, let them crush it,
How else can I find a remedy for injustice?!

Through these lines, Omon Matjon draws attention to the power of the word and of truth. He expresses, through poetic images, that a human being cannot remain silent forever one day, words overflow from the heart. Pain, suffering, and hope are interwoven in the tone of the work. The poet senses injustice, indifference, and falsehood in society, yet despite this, he does not conceal humanity’s urge to speak, to voice the truth.

Truth here is not merely a philosophical concept, but a supreme moral, social, and spiritual value. It is seen as the foundation of human spiritual purity, poetic responsibility, and society itself. Omon Matjon’s poems on this theme have not lost their relevance even today—they call on us to seek truth, to protect it, and not to fear speaking it aloud. Declaring justice openly gradually merges with ideas of patriotism. Now a person considers it an honor to be martyred for the freedom of the homeland. For the hero, the sole aim is that even if his body and soul do not remain in this world, his motherland may endure forever. This becomes Kubro’s inner cry.

The reader is involuntarily drawn to follow Najmiddin Kubro. For the reader, the concept of the Motherland becomes not merely the place of birth, but a value worthy of being preserved as purely as one’s faith. Indeed, this is the power of literature: to convey the poet’s inner pain, embedded in an image, to the reader. Through the image of Shaykh Najmiddin Kubro, Omon Matjon achieves his creative purpose. He confronts the sons of Chinggis Khan Ögedei and Jöbe Noyon with a wrathful address, saying:

“You will not take my banner from my hands; I will trample you like dust. Strike if you will, cut me down, stab my heart!”

My cry and lament will last until the Day of Judgment:

I may die, but do not die, do not die, Khorezm.

This was Shaykh Najmiddin Kubro's final cry.

History tells us that a son of the Uzbek people has never remained helpless anywhere, and that through unique intellect, wisdom, and knowledge, he has astonished even kings. Our ancestors al-Khwarizmi and al-Biruni made immense contributions to world civilization. However, because the necessary conditions for great discoveries did not exist in their time, the inventions born of their intellect and insight turned them, in the eyes of the people, into figures seen almost as magicians. Ignorant rulers and their arrogant courtiers even mocked them shamelessly. The work of Omon Matjon "The Thirteenth Door" tells of al-Biruni, a scholar who overcame an ignorant court through his intellect and wisdom. Al-Biruni, taken to Ghazna, meets Mahmud of Ghazni. In the majestic royal palace, there were twelve doors, twelve chandeliers, and the royal throne. Mahmud of Ghazni says to al-Biruni:

"Well then!" he rose again from his seat.

"Tell me what I am thinking.

Tell me through which one of these doors

I shall leave right now!"

Al-Beruni paused for a moment, wrote something on a piece of paper, then folded it and handed it to the king. The ignorant ruler left the letter with his vizier, summoned the guards, and had a door opened by breaking through the wall behind his throne. He then exited through that door. Because of his impulsive nature, the king soon returned and became curious about what had been written in the letter. He thought to himself that by doing this he had left the scholar in disgrace. However, the following lines were written in the letter:

If someone possesses a throne and crown,

If power and might are supreme,

Whichever way he turns becomes a pilgrimage,

Whichever direction he sets his will there is a path!

Thus, a thirteenth door appeared in the king's palace. The scholar was victorious. Knowledge triumphed over ignorance. To know this secret, the scholar used no magic or sorcery. He simply knew well that such cruelty and narrow-mindedness were to be expected from arrogant, conceited kings whose minds were clouded by pride. Just as the world is full of diversity, the heroes of Omon Matjon differ sharply from one another in their behavior, thoughts, life experiences, and ways of living. This is, in fact, one of the reasons his works are so engaging. The poet avoids directly describing the characters' traits himself; instead, their personalities are revealed through dialogue. The inner struggles of the characters emerge in debates and discussions. This approach feels natural because genuine lyricism is the product of deep human emotion and profound inner experience.

Conclusion

The poems by Omon Matjon are works of depth and meaning, resonating with human suffering. His verses are close to the people because they articulate the universal human experience. The fact that his poems are being set to music and sung reflects their elegance and artistic value. As the poet himself said, he lived with the people and continues to live among them. Although his body has left this world, his spirit still roams among the people, bringing balm to wounded hearts and relief to weary souls.

As the poet himself expressed:

If the heart knows the color of my soul,

It is enough for the people to know who I am.

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